

MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF AL-4.5WT.%CU/10VOL.%SiC_p METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE FABRICATED VIA MECHANICAL ALLOYING TECHNIQUE

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SUMMARY: Metal matrix composite with composition of Al-4.5wt.%Cu reinforced by 10vol.% SiC particulate has been successfully fabricated via mechanical alloying technique. Ethyl acetate was used as process control agent during mechanical alloying. After alloying, the powder was cold compacted, sintered at 600°C, and extruded at 600°C, with an extrusion ratio of 12.96. The extruded rods were solutionized at 520°C for 4 hours and peak aged at 170°C for 19 hours. Through microstructural observations, different stages of alloying were identified in the process. At the early stage of mechanical alloying, SiC_p were observed to be embedded in the matrix. During the final stage of process, SiC_p were continuously refined. Tensile tests showed that the mechanically alloyed material possessed some superior properties in comparison to that which had not been mechanically alloyed. Increase in both yield stress and elastic modulus had been observed.

KEYWORDS: Mechanical Alloying, Aluminium Metal Matrix Composites, Age Hardening.

INTRODUCTION

The development of metal matrix composites (MMCs) has been one of the major innovations in advanced materials for the past two decades [1]. MMCs combine metallic properties (ductility and toughness) with ceramic properties (high strength and high modulus), leading to higher strength, greater modulus, lower density, and better thermal stability. Discontinuously reinforced MMCs hold the additional advantages of lower fabrication cost, and of more isotropic properties than continuous fibre materials. However the commercialisation of short fibre or whisker reinforced MMCs has been slow due to the relatively high costs associated with currently available reinforcements. More recently, particle reinforced MMCs, with their potential as lower cost, characteristic isotropic, high modulus and strength, high wear resistance, and easily fabricated materials, are becoming more attractive and are reaching commercial production stage [2].

Many processing techniques have been developed to produce particle reinforced MMCs in the attempt to optimise the structure and properties [2-4]. Since most ceramic materials are not well wetted by molten alloys, the cost of improving wettability has limited the commercial application of the conventional molten metal methods. Similarly, there are also other methods such as the infiltration techniques and spray deposition processes. In most cases, however,

high control costs in preventing contamination of liquid metal matrix, as well as prohibitively high melting points have constrained the processes to be less commonly used. As a result, powder metallurgy (P/M) process has become more popular [5,6]. However, one of the major problems in production of MMCs using P/M is either the agglomeration of reinforcement particles due to size difference between powders for the matrix and the particles, or static charge on the particles. To achieve homogeneity of particle distribution, several methods may have to be employed, such as a proper choice of the particle size and the use of polar solvents that neutralise the charge on the surface of the particles [7].

Another alternative method to improve particles distribution is to use mechanical milling (MM) or mechanical alloying (MA) technique [8]. MA is a solid state processing technique allowing production of macroscopically homogeneous composite materials starting from various powder mixtures. It is a ball milling process carried out in a dry ball mill for mixing the mixtures. This process involves repeated welding, fracturing and rewelding of powder particles during the high energy collision between balls and the powder particles. The repeated welding and fracturing finally lead to the formation of alloys and a uniform distribution of very fine powder mixture with a finely controlled microstructure after compaction. In addition to the strengthening caused by uniformly dispersed fine particles, the fine grain size and the high dislocation density of the metal matrix, as a result of work hardening of metal powders, also contributed to the strengthening of the MMCs. One of the advantages of MA is the ease of preparation of alloy powders containing both high and low melting point elements. MA was originally developed in the late 1960s to produce oxide-dispersion strengthened (ODS) nickel-based superalloys [9], it has now been shown capable of producing several stable and metastable crystalline and quasicrystalline intermediate phases, and amorphous phases. The crystalline phases produced usually are of nanometer dimensions. All these effects (very similar to those obtained by other non-equilibrium processing techniques like rapid solidification from the melt, vapour deposition, ion irradiation, etc.) lead to improvements in properties of the alloys. The technique of MA is now applied to all types of materials - metals, ceramics, and polymers, and is being actively pursued by industry, academia, and research laboratories all over the world [10-13].

Aluminium alloys based MMCs are one of the particle reinforced MMCs, under development with MA as a processing route [11]. In an investigation of SiC_p reinforced Al-4.5wt.%Cu composite, well homogeneous distribution of reinforcement in the matrix was achieved by using a planetary ball mill for MA processing [13]. In this paper, composites of Al-4.5wt.%Cu reinforced by 10vol.% SiC_p were fabricated by P/M route, via MA technique as the mixing process for the composite powder at different ball milling durations in a planetary ball mill. Comparison was made with composites that processed via conventional blending method. The microstructure, ageing behaviour, and mechanical properties of the composites were examined in the study.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Elemental Al and Cu powder particles with average particle size of 150 and 50 μm respectively were mechanically alloyed with SiC_p of average particle size of 35 μm in a FRITSCH pulverisette 5 planetary ball mill. 40 hardened steel balls of 16 gram each were used in the ball milling process. The weight ratio of ball to powder was about 16:1. The rotational speed of the turn table was 200 rpm. The corresponding relative speed of the vial was 434 rpm. To prevent excessive cold welding during ball milling, ethyl acetate

($\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$) was used as a process control agent (PCA) at various amount for different MA duration. Argon gas was filled into the vial to reduce the oxygen content and therefore minimised the chance of oxidation during ball milling due to temperature rise. After ball milling, the composite powders were cold compacted at about 420 MPa, lubricated with molybdenum disulphide. The green compacts were then sintered at 600°C for 2 hours in an inert environment of forming gas (95% N_2 and 5% H_2). The sintered compacts were hot extruded at 600°C, with an extrusion ratio of 12.96, using dry graphite as lubricant. The morphologies and microstructure of the powder particles after ball milling were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The extruded rods were machined to standard tensile specimens according to ASTM E 8M. The specimens were solution treated at 520°C for 4 hours, quenched into water at room temperature, and then artificially aged at 170°C for various durations. 15T-scale Rockwell superficial hardness testing was used for determination of the duration of peak ageing. Based on the average values of hardness measurement, the specimens were eventually peak aged at 170°C for 19 hours. Tensile testing was conducted using an Instron testing machine for the peak aged specimens and the fractography study was performed using SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphologies of MA Powder Particles

Figs. 1(a) to 1(e) show the typical morphologies of the powder particles after conventional blending (MA 0 hour) and different MA durations (MA of 1, 3, 6 and 12 hours). With MA, the lumpy Cu powder and SiC particles were broken into smaller fragments, and these fragments were more uniformly distributed within the mixture. MA has significantly improved the distribution of SiC_p in the mixture and reduced the extent of segregation in the composite. A reduction in overall particle size can be observed as MA duration increased. The shape of the particles was also changed to be more rounded after MA. Particles with sharp edges were more difficult to be found.

Microstructural Evolution of MA Powder Particles

Figs. 2(a) to 2(e) show the microstructures of the powder particles at different MA durations. Cu powder could hardly be found as it finally formed a solid solution in Al. It can be seen that as the MA duration increased, the number of SiC_p embedded into the Al matrix increased and the particle size of SiC_p decreased. The incorporation of SiC_p into the surface of the matrix powders was due essentially to inlaying of SiC_p into the cold welded soft matrix powder under collision force. With the increase in MA duration, soft particles were eventually severely deformed and embrittled by cold deformation. For MA durations of 1 and 3 hours, SiC_p were not well distributed (Figs. 2(b) and 2(c)). In some areas, large clusters of SiC_p could be found while in other areas little could be perceived. For longer MA duration, due to continuing fracturing and rewelding, distribution of SiC_p became more and more homogeneous (Figs. 2(d) and 2(e)). In addition, a change in shape of SiC_p was also observed. At the beginning of MA, SiC_p were seen to be sharp and angular, with non-uniform particle sizes. They were gradually reshaped to a more rounded form and more uniformly refined with increasing MA duration. After 6 hours of MA, better distribution of SiC_p had been achieved. It can be concluded that agglomeration of reinforcement particles due to size and weight differences of powders from the matrix could be improved via MA process. No clustering of SiC_p could be found from Figs. 2(b) to 2(e).

(a) MA 0 hour

(b) MA 1 hour

(c) MA 3 hours

(d) MA 6 hours

(e) MA 12 hours

Fig. 1: Morphologies of powder particles at different MA durations.

(a) MA 0 hour

(b) MA 1 hours

(c) MA 3 hours

(d) MA 6 hours

(e) MA 12 hours

Fig. 2: Microstructure of powder particles at different MA durations.

Age Hardening Behaviour

The hot extruded bars were solutionized at 520°C for 4 hours and quenched into water at room temperature. Hardness measurement as a function of artificial ageing time at an ageing temperature of 170°C is given in Fig. 3. For those specimens fabricated by conventional blending method (MA 0 hour), the average hardness readings suggest that the MMC achieved the peak age (T6) condition at about 19 hours of ageing time. However for specimens produced by MA technique, there is no significant trend of reaching peak hardness for the ageing duration from 0 to 23 hours. Since the age hardenability is appreciably reduced by MA process in P/M of Al alloy [12], and hence, superposition of age hardening on dispersion strengthening due to MA has not been attained. This is because the presence of fine grain size after MA significantly contributed to the increase in hardness. The other reason is due to high dislocation density resulted from work hardening of metal powders during ball milling. Consequently, further dispersion strengthening by age hardening will not have much influence once the hardness has already exceeded the peak limit due to the saturation of dislocation density. As a result, the overall hardness values obtained for all MA specimens regardless of MA duration, are found mostly to be higher than the peak hardness value of the non-MA specimen (MA 0 hour). Since the T6 condition for all MA specimens could not be accurately determined, the peak aged duration was taken to be the same as the non-MA specimen, which is 19 hours.

Fig.3: Variation of hardness with ageing time at 170°C for the extruded MA specimens

Mechanical Property

0.2% yield stress and Young's modulus of the MMC specimens are given in Fig. 4. It can be seen that except for MA duration of 6 hours, 0.2% yield stresses increase after MA. Young's moduli also increase with MA duration to a maximum value after 6 hours of MA, followed by a decrease. The increase in moduli and yield stresses may be associated with two factors. Firstly, prolonged ball milling led to the homogenisation of SiC_p distribution, an increase in bonding strength between SiC_p and the Al matrix, and to the refinement of SiC_p. Secondly, although the milling vials were protected by Ar atmosphere, existence of oxygen could still be possible due to improper sealing. The residual oxygen would react with Al to form aluminium oxide during milling since new surfaces were formed continuously due to

fracturing of Al particles. Furthermore, the oxygen and carbon that decomposed from the PCA, would also react with Al to form oxide and carbide. These effects could have contributed to the increase in the Young's modulus and yield stress. However, the formation of extra oxide and carbide would decrease the ductility and hence increase the sensibility to produce voids and microcracks. With long MA duration, crystalline size of the particle was refined to nanosize. This refinement of the crystalline size may enhance ductility of the MMC. The Poisson's ratio obtained for the MMC is about 0.3, similar to that of common metallic materials.

MA Duration (hour)	0	1	3	6	12
0.2% Yield Stress (MPa)	219.2	275.8	259.3	217.5	266.5
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	90.0	95.5	99.0	113.0	93.3
Poisson's ratio	0.32	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3

Fig. 4: Mechanical properties of composites at different MA durations

Fractography

Fig. 5 shows the fractographs of the MMC specimens. Generally, fracture is macroscopically brittle, but on a microscopic scale, local ductile fracture of the metal matrix is often observed. Evidence of SiC_p fracture and interfacial failure are also frequently seen. Fig. 5(a) shows the fracture surface of the blended specimen (MA 0 hour). Agglomeration of sharp edged SiC_p in the matrix can easily be observed. These clumps of reinforcement essentially act as large voids in the composite. Large clusters of SiC_p are also more commonly seen on the fracture surfaces of specimens with shorter MA durations. The fractographs suggest that fracture was due mainly to the segregation of SiC_p and/or debonding at the matrix-particle interfaces in conventional blending and at shorter MA duration where a uniform distribution of SiC_p has not been achieved, especially at the locations where weak diffusion bonding between SiC_p took place. Microvoids can also be observed as microvoid coalescence is generally the predominant fracture mode in particulate reinforced MMCs [14]. Almost no agglomeration of SiC_p could be observed after 12 hours of MA. The agglomeration of SiC_p in the matrix and the interfacial bonding strength were improved with increase in MA duration as a result of more SiC_p being well incorporated into and bonded with the matrix materials, leading to the increase in the interfacial strength between Al matrix and SiC_p reinforcement. Hence the fracture mode changes from initial debonding between SiC_p and Al matrix, to inter-particle fracture. For instance, fracture of SiC particles can be seen in Fig. 5(d) (MA 6 hours). This explains partially why the elastic modulus dropped for MA duration of beyond 6 hours. Due to prolong MA, until such time that the particle size of SiC could become excessively refined

and start losing its effect of high modulus property. Stresses applied to the MMC are transferred through the matrix to the SiC_p. Since the modulus of the SiC is higher than that of Al matrix, once fracture occurred at SiC_p, the load would be absorbed by the Al matrix which caused a decrease in the modulus of the MMC. The yield stress was also increased because the work for the fracture of SiC_p (which is stronger than Al), is greater than the weak debonding force at shorter MA duration.

a. MA 0 hour

b. MA 1 hour

c. MA 3 hours

d. MA 6 hours

e. MA 12 hours

Fig. 5: Scanning electron micrograph showing the fracture surfaces of the MMC after tensile test at different MA durations.

CONCLUSIONS

Al-4.5wt.%Cu matrix composite reinforced by 10vol.% SiC_p, with uniform distribution of SiC_p leading to superior properties compared with those processed by conventional blending method, has been successfully fabricated via mechanical alloying technique. In addition, MA processing has been observed to significantly reduce the age hardenability of the MMC. The elastic modulus of the MMC was optimised at a MA duration of 6 hours. Further increase in MA duration would only increase its yields stress.

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